

Architecture and Schematic Composition of monasteries in Bagan Period

Thin Yu Naing*

Abstract

This paper is attempts to illustrate the architecture and schematic composition of Buddhist monastic complexes, especially of Bagan Area. In dictionary, monastery is a building in which monks live together. Bagan is the earliest imperial state of Myanmar. They left many religious buildings and monuments throughout the centuries. The result of this work provides to retrieve the art and architecture of Buddhist monasteries and the ancient priests played an important role, not only on religious affairs but also in political affairs. Besides, the monastery has been an educational distribution place for the live of normal people and the monks. Moreover, the monasteries in Bagan area which still remain in their origin are studied suggests originally. Nowadays, ancient monasteries are being neglected, some are being deteriorated by various effects. Therefore this work also tends to light not only the art and architecture monasteries and their social religion and political condition of Bagan period but also preservation and conservation of the Bagan monasteries to be involved in the list of world heritage.

Introduction

The word “monastery” derived from the Greek word “monazein” (to live alone). Old Myanmar “klon” is aTibeto Chinese word for a large residence and “phonetaw gyi kyaung” in Myanmar and “vihara” in Pali. Modern archaeology demands not only to reconstruct tangible culture but intangible past by means of studying social and ideological systems including religion, ritual art and architecture of ancient people, especially on their great art and architecture directly concerned with archaeological monuments and inscriptions. A mass monument at Bagan, Myanmar’s medieval Buddhist capital, has been more than a thousand religious structures. At Bagan, three arts of painting, sculpture and architecture should be viewed as one. Religious monuments at Bagan take a variety of forms and little survives of the great monastic complexes, palace apartments, rest houses and other scured structures, and nothing survives of the original secular or domestic architecture, all of which had been made from wood. Remaining are the fundamental Buddhist monuments, which were usually made from baked brick though occasionally stone. Firstly, this paper is about art and architecture of Buddhist monastery together with terminology, environmental and background history of monasteries and the Indian style which are related to Bagan monument on the architectural point of views, the origin of Buddhist monasteries and the history of Buddhist monasteries in Bagan. Moreover, there were some articles about the generally distinguished types of architecture in Bagan monasteries. And, there were also explanation about the formation of structures and types of monasteries from architectural point of view. The Bagan Buddhist monasteries are include in traceable and survival buildings.

Location and Geographical factors

Bagan is situated between the east bank of the Ayeyawady River and the Chindwin River in central Myanmar, and it was one of the most important cities in Bagan Period which flourished between the 11th and the 13th centuries AD. According to Myanmar Chronicles, Bagan was founded by the legendary King Pyinbya in 849 A.D, as a small fortified town. The climate favoured the cultivation of plants and permitted cattle breeding. Raw materials for bake of bricks could get in the surrounding. This ancient city has some two thousand Buddhist

* Lecturer, Department of Araechology

monuments. The most of the people of Bagan Period in these areas are Theravada Buddhists, religion and culture was received from India since centuries. Bagan already had full character as center of a kingdom with city walls and permanent structures. The areas under the kingdom in the 9th century may not be very large. Most of the areas along Ayeyawady and Chindwin River basins, and in the 11th century, starting from Anawrahta period, the areas in the northern and north eastern areas in the present Kayah, Shan and Kachin States were ruled by their traditional rulers 11th century as a period of unification an enlarging process, starting from the end of 11th century under Kyansittha, the kingdom went through a peaceful and prosperous time until the fall in the 14th century. Based on these facts, history of Bagan can generally be divided into 4 epochs:

1. The proto historic and foundation period - early part of 1st millennium until the end of 1st millennium AD.
2. Period of unification process and growth - 10th centuryAD until the end of 11th centuryAD.
3. Period of peace and prosperity - end of 11th centuryAD until the end of 13th centuryAD.
4. The downfall period - end of 13th centuryAD until middle of 14th centuryAD.

Historical Background of Bagan monasteries

Historical evidences indicate that both Mahayana and Theravada forms of Buddhism existed among the Pyu since about the 7th or 8th century AD. At Bagan, votive tablets (Aniruddha period) have been recovered, and the scripts of the Sanskrit inscriptions stamped on them are similar to the 9th century AD Devanagari script used in Bengal and Bihar. Therefore, it can be assumed that the Myanmar had some Sanskrit texts and had learnt Sanskrit language the 9th century AD.

Three periods of Bagan history, each has with its own character in art and architecture. In the first period ends by the twelfth century. The second, intermediate period, continued until the beginning of the last third of the twelfth century. The third, “Myanmar period”, lasted until the end of the thirteen century, up to the disintegration of the Bagan kingdom. At first, the monks were wandered around the country and sometimes they stayed at *avāsa* or *arāma* in three months. And then, they settled in a small house for a single resident *sangha*. Next, the unitary *sangha* became plural: with the spread of Buddhism, the monk communities, and they lived at the monastery. In this way, the monks were united and then they introduced the monastic university, where they took teaching, learning, discussing and sharing the literature of the Buddha. Later, these cultures were spread in all parts of the world especially to the Asia. Therefore, the Buddhist art and architecture of India influenced ancient Myanmar, in many ways such as trade route, wars and monks. The Myanmar received Buddhism when Aniruddha conquered Thaton in 1057-58. Historical evidence indicates that Buddhism existed in Myanmar it was inherited from the Pyus and the Mon who were in central Myanmar about the 9th century AD. However, they did not forsake their earlier beliefs. Spirit and naga-worships as well as Brahmanical influence persisted. Moreover, monastery buildings were not only religious buildings but also social and educational buildings. And then, the ancient priests played an important role in religion, education, political, and social affairs. Not only art and architecture of Buddhist monasteries but also the monk’s life in Bagan period, and the monasteries in Bagan area are studied. The earliest monastic building in Myanmar appears to be a brick structure attributed to the fourth century AD, excavated in 1959 in the Pyu city of Beikthano and known as **KKG-**

The Pyu, whose language has only been partially deciphered, had established several cities in Myanmar before the arrival of the Myanmar and could have adopted Buddhism since the second or third century.

Three Kinds of Monasteries in Bagan by Formation of Structures

In fact, in the monastic structures at Bagan, there can be divided into three kinds as follows:

- (1) Monasteries near the significant religious building of stupas, temple etc... that donated by the king for the purpose of maintiang these buildings.
- (2) Isolated monastery, sometime two in double storey that belong to the cells for the residential monk learners around the walls and a hall in the middle part served the class room.
- (3) Large monasteries to lecture the Dhamma of Lord Buddha (pariyatti) within the double series of enclosure wall matched with other religious buildings.

Ancient Bagan's "*klon*" is a Tibeto-chinese word for a large residence. There was probably more variety at Bagan in the forms of monasteries rathee than in any other kind of architecture. Even the brick monasteries (*kulaklon*, Indian monasteries) that survive vary considerably, the native wooden types, which have all perished, were perhaps more varied still. Typological classification of 2038 Bagan period monuments:

Temple	911(48%)
Stupa	524 (28%)
Monasteries	431(22%)
Others	31 (02%)

In Bagan periods, brick monasteries were referred to as a kalakyaung or Indian monastery, presumably because either the original builders of brick work or their occupants were kala or Indians. Kala kyaung, or ok- kyaung as they are known in modern Myanmar, varies in type from a small block-like house set in the enclosure of a stupa or temple, to house an individual monk, or a couple of novices, to a large complex consisting of a variety of structures to house a hierarchy of clerics and their servants and slaves. As have been noted above, Bagan was a city of wood and according to the inscriptions, the majority of monastic structures were made from timber. The immediate prototypes for establishments such as the Somin- gyi must have been of wood.

The houses for the monks were called klon and if it was a brick building it was known as Kula klon_ the Indian monastery. Most of the monasteries however were built of wood with "*sac nay mulw*"_ thatch roof, or with "*mwankhon ta cwan*"_ high and grand wood. In some cases the monastery would be profusely decorated and painted so that it would be known by the name of "*klonprok*"_ the variegated monastery, or "*panpuklon*"_ monastery of wood carvings. The "*kulaklon*" were usually adorned with such decorations and extensions as "*calac*_ flame pediments" over doorways and windows, "*prasat*"_ multiple roofs, "*chanwan*"_ portico, "*tulik*"_ assembly hall, and "*pwattuin*"_ polished pillars. Close to these monasteries were built other buildings like "*sim*"_ the ordination hall, "*pitakatuik*"_ library, "*dhammasa*"_ preaching hall, "*tanchon*"_ rest house, "*carap*"_ alms house, "*kappiyakuti*"_ store house, for the detail of such constructions.

Buddhist monastic complexes in Bagan Area

In Bagan, structural remains in various kinds of buildings unfold archaeological validity and historicity. There are two main types of the structural buildings in Bagan such as secular buildings and religious ones. These religious buildings can be classified into 7 categories such as art of work in Buddhist architecture, namely ceti (stupa), GuPaya (temple), Kyaung (ordination hall), Pitakatuik (library), and Dhammasa (courtyard). Apart from these categories of Ceti and temple, the monastic structure belongs to significant features in its number. There are also in organization of such structures in cluster, architecturally termed as “**complex**” which has been found in a considerable number in Bagan. In the Buddhist monastic complexes combine with the single-cell monastery and multiple-cell monastery. According to their preserved condition, the structural remains can be surveyed in countable number of 10 monastic complexes there which have thrown light on archaeological validity is such as:

- (1) Lemyatnha monastic complex
- (2) HsutaungPyi monastic complex
- (3) Hsinbyu shin monastic complex
- (4) Shwenanyintaw monastic complex.
- (5) Dhammarazaka Pagoda complex
- (6) Sagar monastic complex
- (7) Shwekyauung monastic complex
- (8) Tazaung monastery complex
- (9) Mingalarceti monastic complex
- (10) Myataung monastic complex

Among them, Lemyatnha complex reveals the most characteristics feature in work of art and architecture in such kind of organization, provided by its own materials source of epigraphic evidence and surviving structural remains. Therefore it is presented as example in Buddhist monastic complexes.

The most characteristic feature in work of art and architecture of monastic complex

Lemyatnha complex defines the most characteristic feature in work of art and architecture in such kind of organization. In Lemyatnha monastic complex, totally eight categories of architectural units are found as follows:

- (1) Temple
- (2) Stupa
- (3) Two-storeyed monastery and small monasteries
- (4) preaching hall
- (5) Ordination hall
- (6) Library
- (7) Enclosure wall
- (8) Square tank

Two Types of Monasteries by Architectural Point of View

Monasteries, on the other hand had "their" function. It is a place for the propagation of the Buddha teachings the "*Dhamma*". It is the place where the monks reside and the place where young novices and those new monks, who entered into the order, were trained in the way of Buddha recitation of prayers and taught the teaching of Buddha.

The structure and functions of monasteries also differ very much from the other two types, the temples and stupas. Monastery types should not be ignored, as they are quite significant to be classified and yet to be thoroughly studied. By studying the architectural

formation, the monasteries of Bagan can be grouped into two distinguished types. The two basic types are: _

- (1) Single-cell monasteries and
- (2) The multi-cell monasteries.

The distinction between "single-cell monasteries" and "multi-cell monasteries" can be compared as follows. The primary intention of use and function differed in each case. A single-cell monastery is meant to be resided by a monk or a group of few monks. The size of interior space of the single-cell unit is arranged with a limited function just to suit the needs of its residence. A multi-cell monastery was design to accommodate for a large group of monks, or a group of monks, headed by a chief monk.

The total number of monastery type structures is **415**, which consists of about 22% of the total. If 415 monasteries be classified under two types it is very interesting to find the proportion between the Klon monasteries and the Taik Monasteries as;

Klon monasteries (single-cell monasteries)	387 (93.31%)
Taik-monasteries (multi-cell monasteries)	28 (6.69%).

Nowadays, according to the survey record, there were **422** monasteries structures in Bagan Area.

The architecture of single cell monasteries in Bagan period

When studying the typology of klon monasteries, the approach can only be made upon the brick cell structures which were the only remains that can be seen at the present. By studying the formation of cells, three groups of klon monasteries can be classified as;

- (1) Central cell and corridor
- (2) Non-central cell and corridor
- (3) Cell, divided into two rooms.

The main features of the single cell monasteries

The cells

The floor

Doorways

Perforated windows

Roofs

Niche

The hall

The platform

The architecture of multi cell monasteries in Bagan period

The detail studied should be made to the residential monastery or multi-cell monastery type monuments. The multi-cell monasteries consist of a series of space and a number of cells (generally more than 4 cells).

The main features of the multi-cell monasteries

The main features generally found in the multi-cell monastery can be listed as follows;

1. The cells
2. The entrance vestibule
3. The courtyard
4. The hall
5. The shrine
6. Corridors
7. Stairs

Conclusion

In conclusion, Monasteries play as an important role of Buddhist religious monuments. These monasteries can be divided into three kinds of monasteries by formation of structures. There are (1) monasteries near the significant religious building of stupas, temple, (2) Isolated monastery, and (3) Large monasteries to lecture the Dhamma of Lord Buddha. Moreover, these monasteries can be separated into two types of monasteries by the architectural point of views such as (1) single cell monastery, and (2) multi cell monastery. Therefore, this paper is that the detail studied about the Klon monastery or single cell monastery types. These single cell monasteries were mainly lived by a few monks. And then, these were presented with examples. By studying the typology, two groups of klon monastery can be classified as (1) Non-central cell and corridor and (2) central cell and corridor, and (3) cell, divided into two rooms. The main features of the single cell monasteries are the cell, hall, yard, front door, platform, main niche and pedestal, window, corner pilasters, roof terraces, and timber attic which were explained. Multi cell monasteries were mainly lived by a group monk or students. And then, these were presented with examples. By studying the typology, the multi cell monasteries are rectangular as well as square, and has a large central hall surrounded by cells in addition to the central cell, which may have contained an image. Most of the inner walls and the ceiling of monasteries were properly plastered, painted and decorated with frescos which were explained.

The Buddhist monastic complexes in Bagan were organized by religiously structural units of temple, stupa, ordination hall, *Dhammasa* (courtyard), *Pitakataik* (library), and monasteries for chief monks *Mahathera* and other junior monks very often accompanied by enclosure walls, water tank and sometimes rest-house for the common people. Actually compositional system of their structural units differ from each other_ some with particular building in separate group from minor ones while some with entire buildings in miscellaneous arrangement. Noticeably among them, the structural integration of lay-out plan show the same manner in Lemyatnha and SutaungPyi monastic complex, the importantly major building of ordination hall, temple, and monastery for *Mahathera*, and *Dhammasa* or court-yard inserted in the inner wall and other minor building of monasteries as well as in the outer wall.

Moreover, most of the monasteries were built in Bagan area with various types and styles is mentioned the inscriptions. The ancient people donated many monasteries that decorated with ranging from simple dwellings of wood from Bagan Period to Kon baung period. Monasteries were built with masonry, brick and wood in Bagan period, it is unlikely that their one or two storeyed interior cellular structures and central shrines, served as the prototypes for the development of wooden monasteries. Actually, the product of this paper intends to light the value of art and architecture of monasteries and suggests do preservation and conservation the monasteries that are being neglected and deteriorated day by day.

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Map (1) Map of Bagan Ancient City

Fig (2) Aerial Photo of Hsin byu shin Monastic Complex

Fig (3)

Plan (1) Single-cell monastery

Plan (2) Multi- cell monastery

Section of standard klon monastery Monument no.686

Plan (3)

- 1. Front door
- 2. Main niche
- 3. Lateral door
- 4. Windows
- 5. Flaps
- 6. Corner pilasters

- 7. Frieze
- 8. Ornate molding at cornice
- 9. Sein tone
- 10. Roof terrace

Plan (4) Isometric: exterior of the cell of Monastery no.702

Figure (1) The remain of wood in Shin bo mae monastery

Figure (2). The wall painting of Bagan monastery.

Figure (3) Western view of Shin bo mae monastery

Figure (4) flame pediment of entrance

Figure (5) Perforated window of Myinkaba monastery

Figure (6) water outlet of monastery

Figure (7) cell plan of Soemngyi monastery.

Figure (8) Sand stone floor of Soemngyi monastery.

Figure (9) Eastern view of Tamani monastery Monument no- 1111

Figure (10) Post hole of Tamani monastery Monument no-1111

Figure (11) Mural painting of Tamani Monument no-1111

Figure (12) The brick forming system of vault at Tamani Monument no- 1111

Figure (13) Eastern view of Sin paung monastery

Figure (14) Single cell monastery accompanied with the preaching hall.

Figure (15) stucco carving of Lemyatnha complex